

Laparoscopy as a Diagnostic Tool in Abdominal Conditions: An Observational Study

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Received: 25-08-2024 / Revised: 23-09-2024 / Accepted: 25-10-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Diagnostic Laparoscopy has emerged as a vital tool with high diagnostic accuracy, particularly in cases where traditional imaging modalities fail to provide definitive answers. The use of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool is advantageous where the etiology remains unclear after routine workup. Studies have shown that diagnostic laparoscopy has a high sensitivity and specificity in identifying intra-abdominal pathologies. The ability to perform therapeutic interventions during the same procedure further enhances its utility in improving patient outcomes. Moreover, the introduction of laparoscopic ultrasonography and fluorescence-guided surgery, has further expanded its diagnostic capabilities. Limitations are highly operator and technology dependent with few relative and absolute contraindications.

Aim: This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool in various abdominal conditions, focusing on its utility in detecting pathologies that remain unresolved through conventional radiological investigations.

Materials and Methods: An observational study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery on adult patients undergoing diagnostic laparoscopy for abdominal conditions. Preoperative workup encompassed a comprehensive assessment, including history taking, physical examination, relevant laboratory tests, abdominal ultrasound, X-ray, Contrast Enhanced Computed Tomography(CECT whole abdomen) and when necessary Magnetic Resonance tomography(MRI). The study aimed to enroll a sample size of 117 patients based on statistical calculations. Data collected during the study period was analysed using appropriate statistics. The diagnostic laparoscopy procedure followed standard techniques under general anaesthesia with specific patient and surgeon positioning.

Results: The diagnostic laparoscopy yielded pathological findings across the study population. The majority of the study population was female (88%) and aged between 41-50 years (46.2%). Among the 117 patients examined, 100 (85.47%) displayed discernible pathology, while 17 (14.53%) showed no detectable abnormalities. The pathological spectrum included a range of conditions: ovarian cysts were diagnosed in 19 patients, endometriosis in 27 patients, Koch's abdomen in 9 patients, Meckel's diverticulum in 3 patients, mesenteric lymphadenitis in 10 patients, ruptured liver abscess in 7 patients, appendicular pathology (including inflamed appendix and appendicular perforation) in 5 patients, mesenteric cyst in 3 patients, adhesions (fibrous, flimsy and band adhesions) in 15 patients, and traumatic visceral injuries (splenic injury) in 2 patients.

Conclusion: The study highlighted laparoscopy's crucial role in diagnosing and managing abdominal conditions. It emphasized its minimally invasive nature, precise visualization, and efficacy across demographics and socio-economic groups. Laparoscopy was shown to reduce hospitalization times, post-operative pain, and overall morbidity and mortality rates, effective in identifying predictive factors for pathology detection, contributing valuable insights into improving diagnostic accuracy and optimizing patient outcomes, making it cost-effective and therapeutically beneficial.

Recommendation: Laparoscopy should be considered a primary diagnostic tool in cases of unresolved abdominal conditions, particularly for patients with a history of addiction. Future studies should focus on refining the

selection criteria for diagnostic laparoscopy to maximize its diagnostic yield and minimize unnecessary procedures.

Keywords: Laparoscopy, Diagnostic Tool, Abdominal Conditions, Pathology Detection, Minimally Invasive Surgery.

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Introduction

Laparoscopy has emerged as a cornerstone in modern surgical practice, particularly in the diagnosis and management of abdominal conditions. This minimally invasive technique allows for direct visualization of the abdominal cavity through small incisions, reducing the need for more extensive exploratory surgery. Initially developed as a therapeutic tool, laparoscopy has increasingly been recognized for its diagnostic potential, particularly in cases where traditional imaging modalities such as ultrasound, computed tomography (CT), and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) fail to provide definitive answers. Over the past few decades, the advancements in laparoscopic technology have significantly improved its diagnostic accuracy, making it a valuable tool in both elective and emergency settings.

The use of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool is particularly advantageous in cases of acute and chronic abdominal pain, where the etiology remains unclear after routine investigations. Studies have shown that diagnostic laparoscopy has a high sensitivity and specificity in identifying intra-abdominal pathologies, including conditions like appendicitis, cholecystitis, perforated peptic ulcers, and various forms of peritonitis [1]. Furthermore, it plays a crucial role in the evaluation of chronic conditions such as endometriosis and adhesions, which are often challenging to diagnose through non-invasive methods [2]. The ability to perform biopsies and therapeutic interventions during the same procedure further enhances the utility of laparoscopy, reducing the need for multiple surgeries and improving patient outcomes.

Recent studies have emphasized the role of diagnostic laparoscopy in oncological settings, particularly in the staging of abdominal cancers. For instance, laparoscopy has proven effective in detecting peritoneal metastases and small liver lesions that might be missed by imaging studies [3]. This capability is crucial for accurate staging and treatment planning in cancers of the gastrointestinal tract, pancreas, and liver. Moreover, the introduction of advanced laparoscopic techniques, such as laparoscopic ultrasonography and fluorescence-guided surgery, has further expanded the diagnostic capabilities of this procedure [4].

Despite its advantages, the application of diagnostic laparoscopy is not without challenges. The

procedure is highly operator-dependent, and the quality of the diagnostic outcomes can vary based on the surgeon's experience and the availability of advanced laparoscopic equipment. Additionally, certain conditions, such as extensive adhesions or morbid obesity, may limit the effectiveness of laparoscopy and increase the risk of complications [5]. However, with ongoing technological advancements and increased surgeon expertise, the role of diagnostic laparoscopy is expected to continue growing, providing more accurate and less invasive diagnostic options for patients with complex abdominal conditions.

This study aims to evaluate the effectiveness of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool in various abdominal conditions, focusing on its utility in detecting pathologies that remain unresolved through conventional radiological investigations.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: An observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted in the Department of General Surgery at Rohilkhand Medical College and Hospital, Bareilly, U.P., India.

Study Period: The study was carried out from November 1, 2022, to October 31, 2023.

Participants: The study included all patients who underwent diagnostic laparoscopy for abdominal conditions during the study period at the hospital.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Adult patients above the age of 18 years.
- Patients with indeterminate diagnosis after routine radiological investigations (e.g., X-ray, Ultrasound, CT scan, MRI).
- Patients with acute and chronic abdominal pain.
- Patients with blunt abdominal trauma.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients not fit for surgery (ASA grade 3 and 4).
- Hemodynamically unstable and moribund patients.
- Pediatric patients requiring evaluation of internal genital organs and treatment of disorders of sex development.
- Patients with diagnosed abdominal malignancies.

Sample Size: A total of 117 patients were included in the study. The sample size was calculated using the formula:

- $n = 4pq / L^2$
- p : 92% (p =percentage or proportion) [2] q : (100- p) = (100- 92) = 8% L : Absolute Allowable error (5%) $n=(4 \times 92 \times 8) / 25= 117$

Preoperative Workup: All patients underwent a thorough preoperative evaluation, including:

- Detailed medical history and physical examination.
- Baseline investigations: Hemoglobin, total and differential white blood cell count, ESR, bleeding time, clotting time, HIV, HBsAg, blood grouping, HbA1C, random blood sugar, fasting blood sugar, postprandial blood sugar, blood urea, serum creatinine, urine routine microscopy.
- Radiological investigations: Abdominal ultrasound, Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography (CECT), Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI).
- Informed consent was obtained after explaining the options of treatment.

Surgical Procedure: Diagnostic laparoscopy was performed under general anesthesia using a standard laparoscopic technique:

- **Patient Positioning:** Patients were positioned supine with the arms either tucked or out at a 90-degree angle depending on the area of focus.
- **Entry Technique:**
 - **Open Access (Hassan's Technique):** The umbilicus was held with a tissue-holding forceps, and a 10-12mm transverse incision was made. The fascia and muscles were opened, and a blunt-tipped Hassan's trocar was inserted.
 - **Closed Technique (Veress Needle):** A Veress needle was inserted 2 cm below or above the umbilicus, or at Palmer's point, followed by insufflation with CO₂. The needle was then removed, and a trocar was inserted.
- **Port Placement:**
 - A 10-mm infra-umbilical or supra-umbilical port was used for the laparoscope.
 - Additional 5-mm or 10-mm lateral ports were placed as required based on the suspected pathology.

Figure 1: Appendicular Pathology

Figure 2: Endometriosis

Figure 3: Meckel's diverticulum

Figure 4: Omental adhesions

Figure 5: Band adhesions and fibrous adhesions

Figure 6: Abdominal tuberculosis

Figure 7: Mesenteric lymphadenitis

Figure 8: Ovarian cyst

Figure 9: Mesenteric cyst

Figure 10: Ruptured liver abscess

- **Diagnostic Examination:** A 30-degree laparoscope was used to examine the abdominal cavity.
- **Postoperative Care:** Hemostasis was confirmed, the laparoscope and ports were removed, and the sheath was closed using absorbable sutures. Patients were monitored postoperatively for vital signs and recovery.

Data Collection and Analysis:

- Detailed history, general examination, and systemic examination were recorded for each patient.
- Data were entered into Microsoft Excel, and statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0. Descriptive statistics, including proportions, means, and standard deviations, were calculated. Appropriate statistical tests were applied depending on the data distribution.

Ethical Considerations: Institutional Ethics Committee approval was obtained prior to the commencement of the study. Informed consent was obtained from all participants before they were included in the study.

Result

The study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool in abdominal conditions by analyzing data from 117 patients who underwent Diagnostic Laparoscopy. The findings are summarized in the following paragraphs and tables.

The age distribution of the study population revealed that the majority of patients (46.2%) were in the age group of 41-50 years, followed closely by those aged 29-40 years (45.3%). The youngest age group, 18-28 years, accounted for only 8.5% of the study population (Table 1). This indicates that middle-aged individuals were more likely to undergo diagnostic laparoscopy for abdominal conditions.

Table 1: Age Distribution

Age Group	Frequency	Percentage
18-28 years	10	8.5%
29-40 years	53	45.3%
41-50 years	54	46.2%

Figure 11: Age distribution

The gender distribution highlighted a significant predominance of female patients in the study, with 88% being female and only 12% male (Table 2). This suggests that women were more frequently subjected to diagnostic laparoscopy for abdominal conditions compared to men.

Table 2: Gender Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	14	12.0%
Female	103	88.0%

Figure 12: Gender distribution

The study examined the correlation between gender and the detection of pathology. Out of all the patients in whom pathology was detected, 14 were male and 86 were female. However, there was no significant association between gender and the detection of pathology ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$), indicating that gender did not play a major role in the likelihood of detecting pathology through laparoscopy (Table 3).

Table 3: Correlation of Gender with Pathological Findings

Gender	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected	Total	p-value
Male	14	0	14	0.100
Female	86	17	103	

Figure 13: Correlation of Gender with Pathological Findings

When examining the correlation between age and the detection of pathology, it was observed that pathology was most frequently detected in patients aged 29-40 years (46 cases), followed by those aged 41-50 years (44 cases). However, the statistical

analysis showed no significant association between age and the detection of pathology ($p\text{-value} > 0.05$), indicating that age alone was not a determinant factor for pathological findings (Table 4).

Table 4: Correlation of Age with Pathological Findings

Age Group	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected	Total	p-value
18-28 years	10	0	10	
29-40 years	46	7	53	0.291
41-50 years	44	10	54	

Figure 14: Correlation of Age with Pathological Findings

Out of 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 87 patients presented with pain in abdomen and 13 with no pain in abdomen (Table 5). Out of 17 patients in whom pathology was not found, 15 patients presented with pain in abdomen and 2 patients with no pain in abdomen. The p-value is more than 0.05, hence there is insignificant association.

Table 5: Correlation of Pain in Abdomen with Pathological Finding

Pain in abdomen	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
Yes	87	15	102	0.888
No	13	2	15	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 15: Correlation of Pain with Pathological Findings

Out of 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 29 patients presented with fever and 71 with no complaints of fever. Out of 17 patients in whom pathology was not found, 1 patient presented with fever and 16 patients with no complaints of fever. The p-value is less than 0.05, hence there is significant association (Table 6).

Table 6: Correlation of Fever with Pathological Finding

Fever	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
Yes	29	1	30	0.44
No	17	16	87	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 16: Correlation of Fever with Pathological Findings

Out of 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 29 patients presented with nausea/vomiting and 71 patients with no nausea/vomiting. Out of 17 patients in whom pathology was not found, 3 patients presented with nausea/vomiting and 14 patients with no nausea/vomiting. The p-value is more than 0.05, hence there is insignificant association (Table 7).

Table 7: Correlation Of Vomiting / Nausea with Pathological Finding

Vomiting / Nausea	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
Yes	29	3	32	0.332
No	71	14	85	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 17: Correlation of Vomiting/Nausea with Pathological Findings

Out of 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 14 patients presented with abdominal distension and 86 with no distension (Table 8). Out of 17 patients in whom pathology was not found, 2 patients presented with abdominal

distension and 15 patients with no distension of abdomen. The p-value is > 0.05, hence there is insignificant association

Table 8: Correlation of Abdomen Distension with Pathological Finding

Abdomen Distension	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
Yes	14	2	16	0.804
No	86	15	101	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 18: Correlation of Abdomen distension with Pathological Findings

Out of 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 80 patients had done X-RAY(erect abdomen) , 16 patients underwent CECT(whole abdomen) and 4 patients had done MRI(pelvis) prior to Diagnostic Laparoscopy (Table 9). Out of 17 patients in whom pathology was not found, 2 patients did X-RAY(erect abdomen), 9 patients did

CECT(whole abdomen) and 6 patients did MRI(pelvis) before they were advised for diagnostic Laparoscopy. The p-value is < 0.05, hence there is significant association between the investigations done before performing Diagnostic Laparoscopy and the need for the DL for coming to a diagnosis.

Table 9: Correlation Of Investigation With Pathological Finding

Investigation	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
X-ray / USG	80	2	82	0.000
CECT (W/A)	16	9	101	
MRI	4	6	10	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 19: Investigation with Pathological Findings

Out of 117 patients, 100 patients in whom pathology was detected, 19 patients were diagnosed with ovarian cyst, 27 patients were diagnosed with endometriosis, 9 patients were diagnosed with koch's abdomen , 3 patients were diagnosed with Meckel;s diverticulum, 10 were disnosed with Mesenteric lymphadenitis, 7 were diagnosed with ruptured liver abscess, in 5 patients appendicular pathology(inflamed

appendix, appendicular perforation), 3 patients were diagnosed with mesenteric cyst, 15 patients showed adhesions(fibrous, flimsy adhesions), 2 patients were diagnosed with traumatic visceral injury(spleen injury). 17 patients were there in whom pathology was not found, The p-value is < 0.05, hence it is statistically significant (Table 10).

Table 10: Correlation Of Diagnosis with Pathological Finding

Investigation	Pathological finding		Total	p-value
	Pathology Detected	No Pathology Detected		
Ovarian Cyst	19	0	82	0.000
Endometriosis	27	0	101	
Tubercular Pathology	9	0	10	
Meckels Diverticulum	3	0	3	
Mesenteric Lymphadenitis	10	0	10	
Ruptured Liver Abscess	7	0	7	
Appendicular Pathology	5	0	5	
Mesenteric Cyst	3	0	3	
Adhesions	15	0	15	
Traumatic Visceral Injury	2	0	2	
No Pathology	0	17	17	
Total	100	17	117	

Figure 20: Correlation of Diagnosis with Pathological Finding

Discussion

The study aimed to assess the effectiveness of laparoscopy as a diagnostic tool in various abdominal conditions by analyzing data from 117 patients. The results revealed several key findings, particularly related to the demographic characteristics of the patients and the factors associated with the detection of pathology.

The majority of patients who underwent diagnostic laparoscopy were in the middle-aged groups, with 46.2% of the patients being in the 41-50 years age group, followed closely by 45.3% in the 29-40 years age group. This distribution suggests that abdominal conditions requiring diagnostic laparoscopy are more prevalent or are more likely to be investigated in middle-aged individuals. However, there was no significant association between age and the likelihood of detecting pathology, indicating that while middle-aged patients were more frequently subjected to the procedure, age alone did not significantly influence the detection of abdominal pathology.

The study had a predominantly female population, with 88% of the participants being female. Despite this gender imbalance, the results showed no significant association between gender and the detection of pathology. This suggests that although more women underwent the procedure, the likelihood of detecting pathology was not influenced by gender, highlighting the importance of considering factors beyond gender when evaluating abdominal conditions through laparoscopy.

This prospective observational study analyzed the role of laparoscopy in diagnosing unknown abdominal and pelvic pathologies in 117 patients. The study found that laparoscopy was particularly effective in diagnosing conditions like Koch's abdomen, adhesions, appendicitis pathology and endometriosis, with diagnostic accuracy reaching up to 83.4%. The study concluded that laparoscopy significantly reduced diagnostic delays and postoperative recovery times [6].

A study assessed the utility of early diagnostic laparoscopy for right lower abdominal pain, including suspected acute appendicitis, in 284 patients. The findings indicated that 82% of patients had a positive finding at laparoscopy, with a significant number undergoing surgical interventions. The study emphasized the safety and effectiveness of diagnostic laparoscopy in emergency settings, reducing unnecessary laparotomies and improving patient outcomes [7].

In a study conducted on 60 patients with chronic undiagnosed abdominal pain, diagnostic laparoscopy revealed significant findings in 98.3% of cases, including chronic appendicitis, pelvic inflammatory disease, and endometriosis. The study

highlighted the superior diagnostic ability of laparoscopy, which allowed for both diagnosis and therapeutic intervention during the same procedure [8].

A study from a tertiary care hospital involved 70 patients with chronic abdominal pain. The diagnostic laparoscopy successfully identified the cause in 90% of cases, with conditions such as appendicitis and adhesions being the most common findings. The study underscored the role of laparoscopy in providing definitive diagnoses when other methods fail [9].

A study involved 174 patients with right lower abdominal pain of uncertain diagnosis. Laparoscopy yielded positive findings in 97.7% of cases, with appendicitis and gynecological pathologies being the major findings. The study highlighted that laparoscopy is a valuable diagnostic tool, particularly in cases where non-invasive methods are inconclusive [10].

Conclusion

In conclusion, the study demonstrated that age and gender did not significantly influence the likelihood of pathology detection, emphasizing the importance of clinical judgment and patient history in the decision-making process.

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